

School Heads' Leadership and Innovative Skills in Relation to Teachers' Performance

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Dr. Nonale Q. Resoor

Assistant School Division Superintendent, SDO-Canlaon City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-3855-4177>

Dr. Luis P. Serviñas

Public School District Supervisor, Department of Education, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-4147-6136>

Dr. Enrique Q. Retes

OIC-CID Chief, DepEd Division of Guihulngan City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2193-1556>

Dr. Gerry C. Eltanal

Public School District Supervisor, DepEd Mabinay 4, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-7032-0781>

Abstract:

Leadership is as old as human civilization. Leadership style steers the organization to a higher level of productivity. It breeds cooperation and motivation among employees. This study sought to find out the level of school heads' leadership skills in one of the small-sized School Division Offices (SDOs) in Central Philippines during the School Year 2021-2022. Results shows that the school heads' level of leadership skills in the areas of technical skills, interpersonal skills, and conceptual skills is "high level". The p-value showed no significant difference existed between the school heads' level of leadership skills when grouped and compared according to age, highest educational attainment, and plantilla position, except for the variable sex. Further, there was no significant difference existed between the school heads' level of leadership skills and the level of teachers' performance. Results of this study calls for the School Heads undergo Information Communication Technology (ICT) capability-building; Initiate training on Grievance Machinery; and Conduct a confidence-building activity in problem-solving skills.

Keywords: innovative skills, teachers' performance, technical skills

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The rise and fall of a school rest upon the school head who plays a high-minded role in leadership and management. Distinctly, school heads should possess leadership and innovative skills to function efficiently and efficaciously among others. One of the leadership domains that school leaders should address is the wholesome interaction between school leaders and subordinates that will redound to a result-oriented process and empower the followers toward the attainment of the organizational objectives. Thus, creating a shared vision and strategic plan for the school, in collaboration with the governing body motivates stakeholders in the community (Day & Sammons, 2019).

Apparently, school leadership characteristically centers on the performance of the teachers as they get involved in daily activities that directly affect the growth and development of the students in schools through the direction of the school heads (Lunenburg and Ornstein (2018). The school heads' leadership skills have been identified as critical management skills to motivate a group of people toward the attainment of a common goal (Bello et al., 2016). Many nations are reforming educational innovation because of its effectiveness as a key instrument for monitoring and improving the quality of education (Murage et al., 2017).

Relatively, the innovative skills among school heads also play an important role to orchestrate the direction towards the achievement of the school. They are expected to continuously innovate their practices in changing school environments (de Jong et al., 2020). Therefore, school heads are expected to proactively innovate school practices to maintain educational quality (Serdyukov, 2017). Although, school leadership remains challenging because of the multi-faceted roles of the school heads as specified in the Result-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) in support to the goals and objectives of the Department of Education.

Against the backdrop, the researcher realizes the importance of assessing the level of leadership and innovative skills of school heads. Assessment of these skills points to quality management of schools as associated with inevitable changes and unprecedented challenges. On the contrary, the lack of attention to the nitty-gritty of leadership, supervisory, and innovative skills, causes failures in the delivery of education targets and performance. Hence, the findings of the study will serve as policy direction of the basic education of the country of which this study is purposively conducted.

Current State of Knowledge

Leadership is about inspiring and winning commitment. It is more about personal authenticity and at times recognizing personal fundamental flaws, which limit leadership capacity. It remains for the skilled leader to help people in the organization know pride and satisfaction in their work. Skillful leaders often inspire their direct reports to high levels of achievement by showing them how their work contributes to worthwhile ends. The development of a leader takes time, dedication, and patience (Sammons et.al, 2017). Inside every successful school, one will find a skilled leader. Research findings and school inspection evidence show that leadership skill is critical to a school's success. School effectiveness and school improvement have consistently emphasized the importance of leadership skills (Leneberg and Ornstein, 2018).

Northouse (2020) stressed that leadership skill is an interpersonal influence towards the achievement of a goal or goals. Three important parts of this definition are the terms interpersonal, influence, and goal. Thus, a skillful leader has more than one person or group to lead. Influence is the to affect others. The goal is the end one strives to attain. This definition of leadership skills says that a leader influences more than one person toward a goal. A school leader is not just a figurehead but he or she is a person in authority to provide direction and lead people to attain the vision and mission of the organization. To attain the vision and mission, a leader requires skills in order to function effectively. Innovative skills are special capabilities possessed by a leader to lead and steer his or her employee's capabilities to perform the job. They are considered tools used by the leader in executing his or her duties and responsibilities to lead employees. These skills are needed in a systematic approach to dealing with leadership problems (Abun, 2018).

Innovative skills are practically the types of skills that allow individuals to become innovative in what they do. These are usually a combination of cognitive skills, behavior skills, functional skills, and technical skills. Innovative skills are the ability to generate ideas that create value and improve processes, from inventing the machine to finding a faster route to work. Having innovative skills is an asset in the workplace because they enable one to solve problems and advance knowledge in the field. Innovative skills among principals play an important role. School principals and teachers are expected to continuously innovate their practices in changing school environments (de Jong et al., 2020). Schools operate in demanding and rapidly changing environments. Therefore, school principals and teachers are expected to continuously innovate their school practices to maintain their educational quality (Serdyukov, 2017).

The quality of education is strongly influenced by teacher performance. One factor that supports the improvement of teacher performance is job satisfaction. When job satisfaction is high, it will affect job performance and achieve goals optimally (Mesiono M., 2019). Moreover, according to Azim & Omar (2018), professional teachers' competency is helpful in making teaching methods more effective and successful which helps the learner to improve their learning abilities, enhance their knowledge and polish their skills. Assessment of teachers' performance is necessary to determine the competency of teachers and it is not a straightforward attempt to solely examine students' academic achievement. According to Weisberg (2019), teaching performance is firstly influenced by the quality of the education system. That is schools are about teaching and learning, and all other activities are secondary basic goals. Leadership in instructional matters should emerge freely from both principals and teachers. Teachers deliver the instruction in the classroom, they have expertise in curriculum and teaching, and they have mastered a substantive body of knowledge. Professional conversations and professional development should revolve around the improvement of instruction, how students learn, and appropriate teaching strategies.

Ozgenel (2019) stressed that teachers' performances did not change according to their education level. The result supported and conformed to the study of Hassan et al. (2020), who studied the "The Leadership Style of School Principals and Performance of Teachers", the result concluded that no significant difference between the demographic characteristics of teachers and their performance. Aquino et.al (2021) in their study titled "Managing educational institutions: School Heads' leadership practices and Teachers' Performance" ascertained that teachers' performance is consistent irrespective of age, educational attainment, or significant contributions. Additionally, they elaborated that study on managing educational institutions: school heads' leadership practices and teachers' performance showed that the teachers' very effective performance remains constant, regardless of whether the school heads carry out a very high authentic leadership.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study was anchored to the Trait Theory of leadership by Carlyle & Galton (1869), which emphasizes that the trait model of leadership is based on the characteristics of many leaders - both successful and unsuccessful - and is used to predict leadership effectiveness. The resulting lists of traits are then compared to those of potential leaders to assess their likelihood of success or failure. In relation to the study, school heads possess different characteristics of leadership to be efficient and effective in leading the school's faculty and staff for the success of the school and as evident in teachers' performances. In addition, this study was also anchored to instructional leadership theory by Weber's (1996) emphasizes that the core function of leadership is to improve teaching and learning models that will assist in the attainment of school improvement. It proves beneficial to policymakers, practitioners, and researchers. In this study, this model served as a catalyst for teaching and learning / instructional leadership practices. In relation to the study, school heads practice their leadership skills beneficial for school management for all school activities, tasks, and programs to be implemented to attain the goals of education.

It is also essential for the completion of this study, the utilization of Kirton's Adaptation-Innovation Theory by Kirton (2003). This theory describes a continuum of cognitive styles and approaches to problem-solving, from high adaptation to high innovation. This theory outlined cognition by which one could identify his or her favored approach to problem-solving. This theory believes that all individuals lie on a creativity continuum (below) between high adaptation and high innovation. Individuals at both ends of the continuum are creative, just in a different way. Those with high adaptation prefer to find solutions using established systems, whereas those with high innovation prefer to go beyond the current norms to find new and untested answers to problems. The general leadership shift since Kirton first developed the Adaptation-Innovation model has seen organizations begin to move from valuing the Adaptor more during the 1970s and 1980s, to now placing great emphasis on finding and developing innovators. Kirton himself emphasized greatly that these individuals were both creative within their own cognitive styles, and that no style was better than another. In fact, he believed that both adaptors and innovators were required to solve complex problems. Accordingly, in relation to the study, school heads, and teachers are creative and innovative with the strategies and techniques in performing their roles as school leaders and strengthening their relationship with all the school stakeholders to be more efficient and effective in all their tasks.

Lastly, this study will be anchored to the performance management theory of action by Simmons (2011), it emphasizes the importance of teachers' educational background (SAT scores) and performance characteristics (e.g., value-added contributions to the achievement, based on standardized test scores and compensation and evaluation histories to describe teacher effectiveness. Furthermore, the performance management perspective tends to treat effective teaching as an individual endeavor and thus seeks solutions focused on enhancing the identification and distribution of effective teachers in schools. In relation to the study, teacher boosts their performances in doing their tasks effectively to meet the expectation or satisfaction of their school heads as well as the Department of Education. The teacher exhibits characteristics that are persistent in all aspects of their tasks and responsibilities to develop and improve themselves to be outstanding teachers.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the School Heads' leadership, supervisory, and innovative skills in relation to teachers' performance in one of the small-sized Schools Division Offices (SDO) in central Philippines during the school year 2021-2022. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) the school heads' level of leadership skills according to technical skills, interpersonal skills, conceptual skills; 2) the school heads' level of innovative skills according to work simplification, community linkages, authentic assessment; 3) the level of teachers' performance during the academic year 2020-2021 when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 4) the significant relationship between the school heads' level of leadership skills and the level of teachers' performance; and 5) the significant relationship between the school heads' level of innovative skills and the level of teachers' performance.

Methodology

This section presents and discusses the research design, locale and respondents of the study, data gathering instrument, data gathering procedure, and its validity and reliability the analytical scheme, and the statistical tools used in the conduct of the study.

Research Design

The nature and objective of this study required the application of descriptive research design to determine the level of leadership and innovative skills in relation to teachers' performance in the small-sized division in Central Philippines. It is the nature of this study to determine the conditions of events in the present state. It involves the relationships among the variables being considered in the study as well as the influence of one variable on another. Based on this premise, the researcher considered it most appropriate to use the descriptive research design. According to McCombes (2019), descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon. It can answer what, where, when, and how questions. A descriptive research design is

appropriate for studies that intend to find out what prevails in the present conditions or relationships, held opinions and beliefs, processes and effects, and developing trends. It also seeks to determine relationships between or among study variables, explore causes or phenomena, test hypotheses, and develop generations, principles, or theories on the basis of its findings. The descriptive research design is appropriate for this study as this intends to collect data currently of the existing level of leadership and innovative skills in relation to teachers' performance. Towards this end, items and responses are scaled in accordance with the actual conditions under investigation. The gathered data will be made as the basis for making professional judgments and conclusions.

Study Respondents

The respondents of the study were 206 teachers of one of the small-sized divisions in the central Philippines, with a total population of 442. Since the number of respondents is quite large, stratified sampling and random sampling techniques were used using the Cochran formula to find the sample size. To get the percentage, the respondents coming from each school are divided by the total number of respondents and multiplied by 100. The respondents will be randomly selected by the researcher from each school using the lottery technique.

Instruments

This research study utilized two sets of researcher-made questionnaires in gathering the data. It was subjected to validity (4.89-excellent) and reliability (0.773 for leadership skills and 0.748 for innovative skills interpreted as "high correlation"). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively. The first set of the researcher-made questionnaire assessed the school heads' level of leadership skills in terms of technical skills, interpersonal skills, and conceptual skills as assessed by the Teacher. It was composed of fifteen (15) statement indicators that were captured on a five-point Likert scale. Each of the leadership skills will be assessed through five statement indicators composing the aforementioned fifteen (15) statements. Statement in set A will be for technical skills, set B for interpersonal skills, and set C for conceptual skills. The second set of researcher-made questionnaires assessed the school heads' level of innovative skills in terms of work simplification, community linkages, and authentic assessment as assessed by the teacher. It was composed of fifteen (15) statement indicators that were captured on a five-point Likert scale. Each of the innovative skills assessed through five statement indicators composing the aforementioned fifteen (15) statements. Statement in set A will be for work simplification, set B community linkages, and set C authentic assessment. The teachers' Individual Performance Commitment Review rating for the academic year 2020-2021 was used in this study as secondary data.

Procedure

Data Collection

After the validity and reliability, the research instrument was established. The researcher sought approval through written communication from the School Division Superintendent of the Department of Education, in one of the small-sized Schools Division Offices in Central Philippines. After permission was granted, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaires to each of the identified respondents. Likewise, the purpose of the study was properly explained. Data gathered from the respondents were tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. The raw data were transformed into numerical code guided by the coding manual. This allows computer processing, statistical derivation, and tabular presentation. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software was used in the computer processing of encoded data. Likewise, statistical tables were constructed as per consideration of the objectives that were stated in this study.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of school heads' leadership skills in terms of the technical, interpersonal, and conceptual as assessed by the teachers.

Objective No. 2, used the descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of School Heads' innovative skills in terms of work simplification, community linkages, and authentic assessment as assessed by the teachers.

Objective No. 3, used the descriptive-analytical scheme mean to determine the level of teachers' performance during the academic year 2020-2021.

Objective No. 4, used the relational-analytical scheme and Spearman-rho to determine the significant relationship between the level of school heads' leadership skills and the level of teachers' performance as assessed by the teachers.

Objective No. 5, used the relational-analytical scheme and Spearman-rho to determine the significant relationship between the level of school heads innovative skills and the level of teachers' performance as assessed by the teachers.

Ethical Consideration

Ethics is concerned with morality and standards of conducting research (Kamau, 2018). According to Creswell (2018), ethics in research deals with one's conduct and serves as a guide to one's behavior. The researcher, therefore, strived to adhere to all the ethical procedures required in research of this nature. Informed consent, privacy and confidentiality, anonymity, and responsibility of the researcher were the major ethical issues of concern. In this research, respondents are assured that identifying information will not be made available to anyone who is not directly involved in the study (Trochim, 2021). Confidentiality means that information is restricted normally increases with the degree of sensitivity of the information and with the degree of vulnerability of the research subject. In essence, confidentiality in the relationship between the researcher and the research subject is to be regarded as an obligation for the research and a right for the research subject (Torp, 2015). Respondents were guaranteed that the information they shared will not be disclosed to the public or to anyone for that matter.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data that were gathered consistent with its predetermined objectives.

Table 1
School Heads' Level of Leadership Skills in the Area of Technical Skills

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The school head has the skill in...		
1. utilizing office software like Microsoft Office 365, Google Docs, and other relevant programs like teleconferencing platforms, web design, and search engines.	3.52	High Level
2. creating training activities, documenting important processes, generating programs, projects, and activities, and relaying/presenting the statuses to the stakeholders.	3.60	High Level
3. involving and overseeing teachers in the implementation of classroom and community initiatives and monitor and evaluate progress towards attainment of specific goal.	3.60	High Level
4. facilitating efficiently and accurately gathering data and analyzing information for significant trends or potential issues relevant to the continued operation of the school.	3.74	High Level
5. relaying updates of the programs, projects, and activities to the stakeholders following the chain of command of communication and protocol of accountabilities.	3.66	High Level
Overall Mean	3.63	High Level

As presented in table 1, the school heads' level of leadership skills in the area of technical skills obtained an overall mean score of 3.63, interpreted as "high level". Technically, respondents assessed their school heads' as possessing high-level skills in all items specified. Investigating further the results, the respondents perceived a highest mean score of 3.74 on item no, 4 which states "facilitating efficiently and accurately gathering data and analyzing information for significant trends or potential issues relevant to the continued operation of the school", while the lowest mean score of 3.52 on item no. 1 which states "utilizing office software like Microsoft Office 365, Google Docs, and other relevant programs like teleconferencing platforms, web design, and search engines" and interpreted as "high level". Results in this regard imply that the school heads need to enhance and further develop their skills in the utilization of office software like Microsoft Office 365, Google Docs, and other relevant programs like teleconferencing platforms, web design, and search engines. They must utilize this ICT software as an effective tool to facilitate their data management, easy communication access, and research for wise implementation of programs, projects, and decision makings in their leadership practices. The result conforms to the study of Mojgan, (2020). According to him principals as school leaders have a major responsibility for initiating and implementing school change through the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and be able to facilitate complex decisions to integrate it into learning, teaching, and school administration. Hence, educational leaders need the skill to promote and implement the notion that technology integration is about focusing on future generations and leading teachers to a change in pedagogy. Accordingly, skillful leaders often inspire their direct reports to high levels of achievement by showing them how their work contributes to worthwhile ends. This can be facilitated through the integration of ICT in the workplace (Sammons et.al, 2017).

Table 2
School Heads' Level of Leadership Skills in the Area of Interpersonal Skills

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The school head has the skill in...		
1. ensuring interactions with the teachers and staff, thus making everyone satisfied with the plans, goals, and targets and have ownership of the decisions.	3.64	High Level
2. listening carefully to both sides and using creative problem-solving strategies to ensure insightful solutions to whatever and whenever conflict arises.	3.74	High Level
3. articulating in dealing with complaints by listening and thoroughly expressing compassion towards the issues undertaken.	3.52	High Level
4. conducting activities that promote respectful work environment by collaboration, group facilitation and team building opportunities.	3.62	High Level
5. showing care about teachers' well-being as a critical factor towards school achievements.	3.64	High Level
Overall Mean	3.64	High Level

The results in table 2 disclosed that the respondents assessed an overall mean score of 3.64 in leadership skills in the area of interpersonal skills, interpreted as "high level". Remarkably, school heads give emphasis on item no. 2 "listening carefully to both sides and using creative problem-solving strategies to ensure insightful solutions to whatever and whenever conflict arises" with a mean score of 3.74, interpreted as "high" while the lowest mean score is item no.3 which is on "articulating in dealing with complaints by listening and thoroughly expressing compassion towards the issues undertaken" was rated 3.52 interpreted as "high level".

Based on the result, it can be inferred that the school heads need to develop more skills in listening and expressing compassion to persons involved in order to solve the complaints or issues at hand. They further need to possess and be updated on the necessary knowledge and skills in grievance machinery in order to handle complaints and facilitate amicable settlement effectively. This result conforms to the study of Bunas (2017), when he said listening carefully to both sides and using creative problem-solving strategies, school heads strongly believed that their teaching force will be motivated to work and support each other in order to achieve a common purpose, particularly in the performance of their duties. Furthermore, Dela Cruz's (2016) claimed that school heads need training for school-based management especially procedures for grievance machinery and amicable settlements. These pieces of training will capacitate them to become innovative school heads that will be able to manage to simplify work experience among subordinates. Likewise, it also adheres to the statement of Northouse (2020) that stressed that leadership skills is an interpersonal influence towards the achievement of a goal or goals. A skillsful leader has more than one person or group to lead. This can be made possible through active listening and compassion to persons within and across the organization.

Table 3
School Heads' Level of Leadership Skills in the Area of Conceptual Skills

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The school head has the skill in...		
1. pushing the entire school in the same direction regardless of teachers' individual perspectives, ideals, and goals.	3.53	High Level
2. inspiring, motivating, and encouraging teachers to accomplish tasks based on the strategic directions of the school as reflected in the School Improvement Plan (SIP).	3.73	High Level
3. taking the initiative and providing exceptional supports with positive attitude and exhibit strong moral values in all situations undertaken by the school by providing clear schematic procedures.	3.60	High Level
4. breaking complex issues into smaller components to see how they are interconnected and draw conclusions in order to formulate possible solutions.	3.63	High Level
5. increasing employee satisfaction and productivity by setting a good example.	3.53	High Level
Overall Mean	3.60	High Level

As revealed in table 3, the respondents assessed their school heads' leadership skills under conceptual skills to be "high level" obtaining an overall mean of 3.60. However, a deeper analysis would tell that the respondents assessed the highest mean score of 3.73, interpreted as "high level" on item no. 2 which states, "inspiring, motivating, and encouraging teachers to accomplish tasks based on the strategic directions of the school as reflected in the School Improvement Plan (SIP)". On the other hand, the lowest mean score of 3.53, interpreted as "high level" was on item no. 1, which states, "pushing the entire school in the same direction regardless of teachers' individual perspectives, ideals, and goals. This implies that the school heads must adhere to their

mandate in the performance of their Key Result Areas (KRA), specifically KRA 3 on Accountability and Continuous Improvement. As a person with authority, responsibility, and accountability, the school head shall lead the school to achieve its objectives and targets. This skill is something to be further enhanced by the school heads through benchmarking activities and other professional development strategies.

Blankstein (2019) agrees when he said that school leaders are expected to be change agents and facilitators, who improve conditions for learning through the creation of cultures that allow schools to operate as professional learning communities. That is, school leaders are considered leaders of leaders. They are expected to bring out the leadership potential of every teacher and employee in the building and work collaboratively with them so that the school ends up making better decisions and is committed to continuous improvement. Consistently, Lenenberg and Ornstein, (2018) postulated that that leadership skill is critical to a school's success. School effectiveness and school improvement have consistently emphasized the importance of leadership skills specifically in manifesting conceptual skills which are necessary in programming the development plans and strategic directions.

Table 4
School Heads' Level of Innovative Skills in the Area of Work Simplification

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The school head has the skill in...		
1. distributing the workloads easily among teachers so that better and more effective work can be done.	3.83	High Level
2. utilizing available resources for faster and immediate action and solutions to the problem that arises.	3.51	High Level
3. designing specific action plan to make the workload easier to accomplish.	3.57	High Level
4. organizing team of teachers who can manage and help in accomplishing the task.	3.76	High Level
5. acting systematically in approaching and dealing with problems that may occur in under his/her leadership.	3.27	High Level
Overall Mean	3.59	High Level

In the area of Work simplification, table 4 shows that the respondents assessed an overall mean score of 3.59 and interpreted as a "high level". Notably, all items are rated "high level". Of these items, school heads put a premium on item no. 1 which state "distributing the workloads easily among teachers so that better and more effective work can be done" with the obtained mean score of 3.83. The lowest mean score is on item no. 5 which states "acting systematically in approaching and dealing with problems that may occur in under his/her leadership" with a mean score of 3.27. This result implies that school heads need capability-building activities through conducting pieces of training, lac sessions, and technical assistance on systematically dealing with problems in the school organization since per records of the Schools Division Office (SDO) school heads do not have training for the past 5 years regarding this aspect specifically dealing with the grievances of the teachers.

Abun (2018), support this result when he said that a leader is not just a figurehead but he or she is a person in authority to provide direction and lead people to attain the vision and mission of the organization. To attain the vision and mission, a leader requires skills in order to function effectively. Innovative skills are special capabilities possessed by a leader to lead and steer his or her employee's capabilities to perform the job. They are considered tools used by the lead executing his or her duties and responsibilities to lead employees. These skills are needed in a systematic approach to dealing with problems. Likewise, Innovative skills among principals play an important role. School principals and teachers are expected to continuously innovate their practices in changing school environments. Schools operate in demanding and rapidly changing environments. Therefore, school principals and teachers are expected to continuously innovate their school practices to maintain their educational quality (Serdyukov, 2017).

Table 5
School Heads' Level of Innovative Skills in the Area of Community Linkages

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The school head has the skill in...		
1. maintaining a good relationship with the LGUs for continuity of services and programs for the entire school year.	3.70	High Level
2. communicating with LGUs and other stakeholders about the concerns of the school regarding programs, projects and activities.	3.60	High Level
3. fostering community linkages for alignment of programs and curriculum to support	3.53	High Level
4. building partnerships with the different stakeholders for the benefit of the school and the students to succeed in their academic endeavors.	3.64	High Level
5. asking for support from stakeholders, especially in the LGUs for the	3.63	High Level

realization of programs and activities of the school.

Overall Mean	3.62	High Level
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Table 5 presents the result of the area of Community Linkages. This area yielded an overall mean of 3.62 and is interpreted as a "high level". With this rating, we can assume that are doing their task as a mandate in R.A 9155 and a part of the requirements in the School-Based Management (SBM) practices which is to establish community linkages and seek stakeholders' support for school continuous improvement. All items were rated "high level" with item no. 1 on top of the rank. This states "maintaining a good relationship with the LGUs for continuity of services and programs for the entire school year" with a mean score of 3.70, interpreted as "high level". The lowest in the rank is item no 3 which states "fostering community linkages for alignment of programs and curriculum to support" obtaining a mean score of 3.53 or "high level". This implies that school heads are tapping stakeholders to support tangible projects, not so much with curriculum enhancement provisions. Hence, this aspect is something to be improved. This means that school heads must ensure that projects contribute to curriculum implementation, the ultimate reason for DepEd's existence.

This result is supported by the statement of Little (2019) that says community collaboration with schools complements and reinforces values, culture, and the learning opportunities that schools can provide for their students. When schools and community organizations work together to support learning, everyone benefits. Partnerships can serve to strengthen, support, and even transform individual partners, resulting in improved program quality, more efficient use of resources, and better alignment of goals and curricula (Miller, 2019). Further, It is essential for school leaders to be agile and adapt their leadership practice to meet the needs of the students, stakeholders, and school systems (Hallinger & Walker, 2017).

Table 6
School Heads' Level of Innovative Skills in the Area of Authentic Assessment

Areas	Mean	Interpretation
The school head has the skill in...		
1.responding actively in the department to DepEd's programs, projects, and activities that pave way for the improvement and development of skills in performing his/her duties and responsibilities as a school leader.	3.54	High Level
2.ensuring consistent actions through strategic monitoring and evaluation of all the concerns of the faculty regarding school programs, projects, and activities.	3.66	High Level
3.making himself/herself flexible enough to monitor and evaluate the faculty and staff performances and suggesting possible measures for further improvement.	3.47	High Level
4.implementing updated Department of Education orders, agenda, and curriculum mandates with constant assessment for a better outcome.	3.67	High Level
5.performing his duties and responsibilities as a leader in evaluating the over-all performance of the school for policy planning and strategic decision making.	3.60	High Level
Overall Mean	3.59	High Level

Table 6 exposes the results relative to the school heads innovation skills in the area of Authentic Assessment which is rated as "high level" as it bears the overall mean of 3.59. To scrutinize further, it is displayed in the table that item no. 4 which is "implementing updated Department of Education orders, agenda, and curriculum mandates with constant assessment for a better outcome" obtained a mean score of 3.67, which is interpreted as "high level". The lowest mean score is 3.47, interpreted as "high level" which is on item no. 3 that states "making he/she flexible enough to monitor and evaluate the faculty and staff performances and suggesting possible measures for further improvement". This result implies that school heads are a little bit slow when it comes to evaluating the faculty and staff performance. They tend to let their teachers do at their own pace when it comes to teaching-learning. School heads are cautious in giving suggestions to teachers for improvement. This can be seen in their observation sheets that all entries are positive. They do not give notes or constructive criticisms for points for improvement. Hence, teachers tend to assume that all their actions are in adherence to the DepEd's policies and standards. Moreover, school heads tend to be bookish in their management. They do not accept innovations from teachers.

Findings conform with the conclusions of Ampofo, (2018) that revealed that school heads poorly supervised lesson preparations to teachers. Instructional documents such as lesson plans/notes and schemes of work were hardly inspected and school heads moderately supervised teachers' lessons by ensuring teachers' punctuality, effective use of instructional time, and delivery of lessons in accordance with prepared lesson plans/notes. School heads are not suggesting strategies for improvement. Contrary to Fullan, (2016) who strongly advocated that school principals must have a vital role in creating suitable conditions for innovation processes and in leading these processes. In addition, the school principals must decide and direct, and assume overall responsibility for their school's educational quality and the establishment of essential innovation conditions.

Furthermore, the Implementation of academic supervision by principals on teachers is essential to improve teacher performance abilities and learning quality through a good learning process along with authentic assessment. In the implementation of supervision, the principal must treat teachers as people who have the potential to progress and develop better so that the emphasis on activities accompanied by reliable and authentic assessment is directed toward the process of improvement (Hoque et al., 2020).

Table 7
Level of Teachers' Performance During the Academic Year 2020-2021 When Grouped According to Age, Sex, Highest Educational Attainment, and Plantilla Position

Variables	Categories	Mean	Interpretation
Age	Younger	4.41	Very Satisfactory
	Older	4.40	Very Satisfactory
Sex	Male	4.39	Very Satisfactory
	Female	4.41	Very Satisfactory
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	4.42	Very Satisfactory
	Higher	4.40	Very Satisfactory
Plantilla Position	Lower	4.42	Very Satisfactory
	Higher	4.39	Very Satisfactory

Table 7 illustrates the level of teachers' performance when grouped according to the respondents' profiles. It can be seen in the table that the teachers' performance ratings are within the bracket "very satisfactory". According to age, there was a very satisfactory performance obtained by the younger teachers (4.41) and older teachers (4.40). Likewise, sex showed a very satisfactory result with a mean of 4.39 (male) and 4.41 (female). In addition, the group with the Highest Educational Attainment achieved a very satisfactory performance with a mean of 4.42 (lower) and 4.40 (higher). Lastly, the plantilla position obtained a very satisfactory result with a mean of 4.42 (lower) and 4.39 (higher). These findings implied that regardless of the respondents' profile, they maintain very satisfactory performance in all success indicators. In addition, teachers ensure an improving performance despite the differences in age, sex, highest educational attainment, and plantilla position. Likewise, this provides data for future promotion endeavors. It is a requirement for promotion to have a 3 consecutive very satisfactory performance rating. Additionally, this result agreed with Casting's (2018) study, which claimed that the performance of teachers is different from other organizations; thus, education is difficult to measure and control. He also emphasized the diversity of other factors that affect a good teaching and effective learning environment. The study of Sabio (2020) on Assessing Elementary School Teachers' Performance Using CBPAST and IPCR: A Five-Year Trajectory Report revealed that the public-school elementary teachers generally yielded a "Very Satisfactory" rating in CBPAST and IPCR during the five-year period. Since the two instruments (i.e. CBPAST and IPCR) are both self-assessment tools, it is recommended that a more subjective performance assessment tool be utilized like those that involve the participation of the students and the immediate superior of the concerned public school teachers. In the study of Baluyos et al (2019) on Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Work Performance, it was revealed that the teachers were highly satisfied with their job, and their work performance was very satisfactory.

Table 8
Relationship Between the School Heads' Level of Leadership Skills and the Level of Teachers' Performance

Correlates	N	<i>rho</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Level of Significance	Interpretation
School Heads' Level of Leadership Skills	206	0.028	0.685	0.05	Not Significant
Level of Teachers' Performance	206				

Table 8 presents the relationship between the school heads' leadership skills and teachers' performance. The data revealed that there is no significant relationship between the school heads' leadership skills and teachers' performance by obtaining a *p*-value of 0.685, which was higher than the alpha level of 0.05. Therefore, the hypothesis states, "there is no significant relationship between the school heads' level of leadership skills and the level of teachers' performance" is accepted. The result indicates that the school heads' leadership skills have no bearing on the teachers' performance if not translated or rendered into actions. This means that there is a need to further translate these skills into behaviors and mechanisms which will be step-by-step followed so that these skills will be of significant influence on the teachers' performance will be achieved.

Furthermore, the result can be explained that teachers' performance can be determined with approved key indicators in the IPCRF with or without the intervention of the school heads. Therefore, the hypothesis, "There is no significant relationship between the school heads' level of leadership skills and teachers' performance" was accepted. Additionally, the results conformed to the study of Aquino et al. (2021) on their study on managing educational institutions: school heads' leadership practices and teachers' performance showed that the teachers' very effective performance remains constant, regardless of whether the school heads carry out a very high authentic leadership. Results contradict the study of Malabarbas et.al, (2022) on the managerial and leadership skills of school heads and the performance of teachers that revealed that school leaders' leadership skills were rated as "always"; this indicates that school leaders demonstrated effective leadership skills, as assessed by the teachers. In addition, the study disclosed a significant correlation between the managerial skills of school leaders and teachers' performance

Table 9
Relationship Between the School Heads' Level of Innovative Skills and the Level of Teachers' Performance

Correlates	N	<i>rho</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Level of Significance	Interpretation
School Heads' Level of Innovative Skills	206				
		0.022	0.757	0.05	Not Significant
Level of Teachers' Performance	206				

Table 9 reveals the relationship between the school heads' level of innovative skills and the level of teachers' performance. The data showed no significant relationship between the school heads' innovative skills and the teachers' performance, with a *p*-value of 0.757, higher than the alpha value of 0.05. The finding inferred that school heads' innovative skills do not significantly contribute to and influence teachers' performance. Therefore, the hypothesis, "There is no significant relationship between the school heads' level innovation skills and level of teachers' performance," is accepted. The study by Pardosi (2021) entitled "Effective principal leadership behaviors to Improve Teachers' Performance and Student Achievement" shed light and clarified the findings of this study that states the effectiveness of the principal's leadership behavior pattern makes a very important contribution to improving the quality of teacher performance and school achievement. Leadership behavior is the ability of principals to influence and direct teachers and all elements effectively and efficiently in order to achieve school goals together. To improve teachers' performance, a principal as the leader must have certain behaviors to accommodate the goal-oriented teaching-learning environment. Hence, innovative skill as a state of being capable will not be enough to influence teachers' performance, instead leadership behaviors are needed. Innovative skills are a state of mind that will not give an impact or result when not translated into approaches, practices, and strategies. Unfortunately, it remains unknown as to what kinds of successful and effective principal leadership behaviors will motivate teachers in improving their performance. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a further study to find the successful and effective leadership behaviors of school principals in accordance with the socio-cultural conditions of schools and teachers and other aspects that influence them.

Conclusions

On the bases of the foregoing findings of the study, the researcher arrived at the following conclusions: It is apparent that the leadership and innovative skills of school heads were found high revealing the momentum of effective and efficient school-based management as evidenced by their capability-skill for the actual exercise of technical, interpersonal, and conceptual competence. Leadership skills thoroughgoing complement and supplement their innovative skills in work simplification, community linkages, and authentic assessment. All these areas and dimensions are determinants of the delivery of their Key Result Areas (KRA). The respondents' performance rating in the School Year 2020–2021 was very satisfactory and at par with all key indicators in the Individual Performance Commitment Rating (IPCR). This was brought about by their desire to be promotion-ready with the possible implementation of the proposed Teacher 1 to Teacher 7 positions and Master Teacher I to V positions which salary grades become financially inviting. Finally, it was instantiated that the school heads' leadership and innovative skills did not directly influence the increase in the level of teachers' performance. Reality demands that these skills have to be translated into the school's strategic plans and actual implementation for teachers' enculturation of continuous professional development. Results of this study calls for the School Heads undergo Information Communication Technology (ICT) capability-building; Initiate training on Grievance Machinery; and Conduct a confidence-building activity in problem-solving skills.

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